

A Highly Efficient Osmium Tetroxide Catalyzed Oxidation of Sterically Hindered Olefins to Diols*

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The use of trimethylamine oxide as oxidizing agent in the presence of catalytic amounts of osmium tetroxide and pyridine in refluxing aqueous *t*-butyl alcohol efficiently converts sterically hindered olefins to diols without forming the α -hydroxy ketones or other by-products encountered with previously known procedures. Trisubstituted olefins with which this procedure has proved successful include α -pinene, the methyl and methoxyethoxymethyl ethers of nopol, ethyl chrysanthemumate, and, marginally, 3-methyl-3-penten-2-one. The disubstituted olefins cyclooctene and *E*-4-methyl-2-pentene were hydroxylated efficiently. The new procedure also proved more efficient than *t*-butyl hydroperoxide for hydroxylation of tetramethylethylene. Pyridine not only failed to enhance but substantially reduced the relatively mediocre yield of diol from α -pinene when *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide was used as oxidizing agent.

THE *syn*-dihydroxylation of olefins with a stoichiometric amount of osmium tetroxide is generally efficient and useful¹, provided the product rivals gold in value. Osmium tetroxide catalyzed hydroxylations utilizing hydrogen peroxide or sodium chlorate as oxidizing agents are often practical with unhindered olefins, but tend to produce substantial amounts of α -hydroxy ketones and carbon-carbon bond cleavage products from trisubstituted olefins¹. VanRheenen, Kelly and Cha have recently reported a particularly mild catalytic procedure with *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide², and Sharpless and co-workers have found *t*-butyl hydroperoxide to be a useful oxidizing agent^{3,4}.

Our interest in this problem was prompted by the need for a chiral diol which could form boronic esters to be used in a new approach to directed chiral synthesis^{5,6}. α -Pinene derivatives have yielded high chiral selectivities in hydroborations⁷, and cation chelation has been found to increase selectivity in directed chiral displacement reactions⁸. These considerations led us to attempt the hydroxylation of nopol derivatives (1).

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Osmium tetroxide (TOXIC) purchased in 1 g ampoules was dissolved in *t*-butyl alcohol to make a 2% solution, measured volumetrically. 60 MHz ¹H nmr spectra were recorded with a Varian EM-360 instrument, and 100 MHz ¹H nmr spectra on a JEOL MH-100. Microanalyses were by Galbraith Laboratories, Knoxville, Tennessee.

Nopol methoxyethoxymethyl ether (1a): A solution of 50 mmol of nopol in THF was treated with 60

mmol of butyllithium at 0° followed by 60 mmol of methoxyethoxymethyl chloride. After 1 hr, water was added and the product was extracted with ether and distilled, b.p. 88-90° (0.1 torr), 74%; 60 MHz nmr (CCl₄): δ 0.86 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.19 (d, *J*=8Hz, 1, CH), 1.30 (s, 3, CH₃), 2.13-2.23 (m, 7, CH, CH₂), 3.35 (s, 3, OCH₃), 3.55 (m, 6, OCH₂), 4.71 (s, 2, OCH₂O), 5.33 (m, 1, C=CH). Anal. Found: C, 70.74; H, 10.12. Calcd. for C₁₅H₂₆O₅: C, 70.82; H, 10.31%.

Nopol methoxyethoxymethyl ether diol (2a):
A. *With stoichiometric osmium tetroxide*: A solution of 0.50 mmol of nopol MEM ether (1a) and 0.55 mmol of osmium tetroxide in 2ml of pyridine was kept at 20-25° 11 hr and then treated with excess aqueous sodium bisulfite. The diol (2a) was isolated by preparative tlc on silica gel, 83%; nmr (CCl₄): δ 0.95 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.28 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.4-2.6 (m, 8, CH, CH₂), 3.38 (s, 3, OCH₃), 3.3-4.2 (m, 9, OCH₂, CHOH, OH), 4.71 (s, 2, OCH₂O); ir (neat) 3420 (OH). Anal. Found: C, 62.20; H, 9.56. Calcd. for C₁₅H₂₈O₅: C, 62.47; H, 9.79%.

B. *With t-butyl hydroperoxide*: A solution of 0.50 mmol of 1a, 0.4 mmol of 70% *t*-butyl hydroperoxide and 0.35 mg of osmium tetroxide in 2 ml of *t*-butyl alcohol was stirred 2 hr at -5° to -10° and then treated with sodium bisulfite. TLC separated 2a (42%) from less polar by-products, which appeared to include substantial amounts of α -hydroxy ketone (3a). On a 40 mmol scale, the yield of 2a fell to 19%.

C. *With permanganate*: A solution of 0.5 mmol of 1a in 6 ml of *t*-butyl alcohol was added to a vigorously stirred solution of 0.73 mmol of potassium permanganate and 3.6 mmol of sodium hydroxide in 10 ml

* Dedicated to Professor R. C. Mehrotra on his 60th birthday in recognition of his contributions to Chemistry.

of water at 0°, stirred 10 min, treated with sulfur dioxide to decolorize, saturated with sodium chloride and extracted repeatedly with ether. TLC yielded 40% **2a** and substantial amounts of less polar by-products.

D. With trimethylamine N-oxide (No pyridine): A solution of 1 mmol of **1a**, 1.06 mmol of trimethylamine N-oxide and 0.8 mg of osmium tetroxide in 0.16 ml of *t*-butyl alcohol, 0.4 ml of acetone and 0.5 ml of water was stirred 7 days. TLC analysis showed no **2a**. Refluxing 30 hr followed by work-up with bisulfite and tlc yielded 27% **2a**.

E. With trimethylamine N-oxide/pyridine. The general preparation of diols (below) was followed, 24 hr reflux, except that the **2a** was chromatographed of silica before kugelrohr distillation, bath 130-140° yielded 62% **2a**.

Attempted oxidation of nopol tosylate (1c) with potassium perchlorate: Treatment of nopol with toluenesulfonyl chloride in pyridine yielded **1c**. The compound is a low-melting solid (from ether/petroleum ether). 60 MHz nmr (CDCl₃+CCl₄): δ 0.80 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.10 (d, *J*=8 Hz, 1, CH), 1.27 (s, 3, CH₃), 2.0-2.4 (m, 7, CH, CH₂), 2.49 (s, 3, ArCH₃), 4.09 (t, 2, OCH₂), 5.35 (m, 1, C=CH), 7.47+7.90 (d, d, *J*=8Hz, 2+2). A 2 mmol sample of **1c** with 2.5 mmol of potassium perchlorate and 2.5 mg of osmium tetroxide in 5 ml of water and 5 ml of THF after 24 hr at 20-25° showed only unchanged **1c** on tlc.

Nopolmorpholine: A solution of 50 mmol of nopol tosylate and 100 mmol of morpholine in 100 ml of THF was refluxed 20 hr, concentrated, treated with water, extracted with ether, and distilled, 74%, b.p. 92-93° (0.05 torr); 100 MHz nmr (CCl₄): δ 0.82 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.12 (d, *J*=8 Hz, CH), 1.24 (s, 3, CH₃), 2.0-2.3 (m, 13, CH, CH₂, NCH₂), 3.48 (m, 4, OCH₂), 5.07 (m, 1, C-CH). Anal. Found: C, 76.23; H, 10.65; N, 5.70. Calcd. for C₁₅H₂₅NO: C, 76.55; H, 10.71; N, 5.95%. Attempted oxidation of this compound (0.5 mmol) with *t*-butyl hydroperoxide (0.8 mmol) and osmium tetroxide (0.05 ml of 0.5% solution in *t*-butyl alcohol) in the presence of tetraethylammonium hydroxide (0.05 ml of 20% aq. solution) at -5 to -15° 2 hr followed by treatment with sodium bisulfite yielded a mixture of products, as shown by tlc and the presence of a strong carbonyl absorption at 1710 cm⁻¹.

General preparation of diols: A solution of 25 mmol of the olefin, 34 mmol (3.75 g) of trimethylamine-N-oxide dihydrate, 1 ml of 2% osmium tetroxide in *t*-butyl alcohol and 2 ml of pyridine in 15 ml of water and 50 ml of *t*-butyl alcohol was refluxed 9-48 hr¹⁷, cooled to 25°, treated with 20 ml of 20% aqueous sodium bisulfite, concentrated under vacuum to remove *t*-butyl alcohol, saturated with sodium chloride and

extracted with ether (4-6 portions). Kugelrohr distillation yielded pure diol, with no by-products detectable by tlc.

Nopol methyl ether diol (2b): Nopol methyl ether (**1b**)¹⁸ was prepared by treating nopol with sodium hydride in THF followed by methyl iodide: 60 MHz nmr (CCl₄): δ 0.84 (s, 3, CCH₃), 1.17 (d, *J*=8 Hz, 1, CH), 1.30 (s, 3, CCH), 2.3 (m, 7, CH, CH₂), 3.29 (s, 3, OCH₃), 3.5 (m, 2, CH₂O), 5.35 (unresolved m, 1, C=CH). The general preparation of diols, scaled up to 0.1 mol of **1b**, 17 hr reflux, kugelrohr bath 105° (0.2 torr), yielded 78% **2b**; 60 MHz nmr (CCl₄): δ 0.93 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.27 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.4-2.6 (m, 8, CH, CH₂), 3.39 (s, 3, OCH₃), 3.6-4.2 (m, 5, CH₂O, OH, CHOH). Anal. Found: C, 67.05; H, 10.37. Calcd. for C₁₂H₂₂O₃: C, 67.26; H, 10.35%.

Pinanediol (5): (+)-*a*-Pinene (**4**) in the general procedure, 0.2 mol scale, 17 hr reflux, yielded 94% **5** on simple distillation, b.p. 90-91° (0.25 torr), m.p. 54-55.5°¹⁹. (See large scale preparation below for further data).

cis-Cyclooctane-1, 2-diol. Cyclooctene, 9 hr reflux, kugelrohr bath 90° (0.4 torr), yielded 85% *cis*-cyclooctane-1,2-diol, m.p. 77-78° (lit.²⁰ m.p. 79°).

threo-4-Methylpentane-2, 3-diol. *E*-4-Methyl-2-pentene, 10 hr reflux, kugelrohr bath 80° (0.75 torr), yielded 78% *threo*-4-methylpentane-2,3-diol, m.p. 56-57.5° (lit.²¹ m.p. 59°).

Ethyl chrysanthemumate diol (7). Ethyl chrysanthemumate (**6**), 24 hr reflux, kugelrohr bath 100-105° (0.25 torr), yielded 91% diol **7** as an oil; nmr (CCl₄): δ 1.2 (m, 16, CCH₃ + C₂CH), 1.93 (s, 1, CHCO₂Et), 3.4 (m, 3, CHOH + OH), 4.17 (q, 2, CH₂O). Anal. Found: C, 62.56; H, 9.59. Calcd. for C₁₂H₂₂O₄: C, 62.58; H, 9.63%.

Pinacol: Tetramethylethylene, 23 hr reflux, simple distillation, yielded 91% pinacol contained in a mixture with ~10% pyridine by nmr analysis; redistilled, b.p. 108-110° (62 torr), 83%, nmr same as authentic sample.

3-Methylpentane-2,3,-diol-4-one: *E*-3-Methyl-3-penten-2-one²² (30 mmol) was subjected to the standard conditions with 3.8 g (34 mmol) of trimethylamine oxide, modified by reducing the amount of water to 10 ml, 18 hr reflux, resulting in a black mixture (containing no unchanged enone by tlc analysis), which was concentrated and chromatographed on silica with ether before distillation, b.p. 60 (0.2 torr) [lit.²³ 65° (1.5 torr)]; 60 MHz nmr (CCl₄): δ 1.13 (d, *J*=6 Hz, 3, CHCH₃), 1.15 (s, 3, CCH₃), 2.18 (s, 3, COCH₃), 3.6 (broad s, 2, OH), 3.88 (q, 1, CHCH₃).

Pinanediol (5) (Large scale preparation). A mixture of 272.5 g (2 mols) of *a*-pinene²⁴, 230 g (2.07 mols) of trimethylamine oxide dihydrate, 1 g of osmium

tetraoxide, 1.5 l of *t*-butyl alcohol, 150 ml of pyridine and 300 ml of water was refluxed gently with stirring (there being a small aqueous phase present) for 4 days. After cooling, the mixture was stirred with 20 g of sodium bisulfite 1 hr more (until the dark osmate color faded to yellow), and enough sodium chloride (~60 g) was added to saturate the aqueous phase, which was then separated and extracted with two 100 ml portions of ether. The organic phase was combined with the ether extracts and concentrated under reduced pressure. Pinane-diol (5) was distilled rapidly at 110-116° (0.3-1.0 torr), forcing the last few grams over with the aid of a heat gun, leaving only a small high-boiling residue, solidified, yield 328 g (96.5%)²⁵. TLC analysis (ether/petroleum ether on silica gel) showed a single spot; nmr (CDCl₃): δ 0.93 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.26 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.29 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.5-2.5 (m, 6, CH, CH₂), 2.9 to 3.8, dependent on concentration (broad s, 2, OH), 3.93 (d of d's, J=6 and 9 Hz, CHOH).

methoxyethoxymethyl (MEM) ether (1a) was readily converted to the diol (2a) (83%) by a stoichiometric amount of osmium tetraoxide in pyridine¹, but the known catalytic methods were found mediocre or worse. Sodium chlorate^{1,9} yielded 10% 2a. *t*-Butyl hydroperoxide and tetraethylammonium hydroxide³ yielded 19-42% 2a, accompanied by comparable amounts of less polar material presumed to be the α-hydroxy ketone (3a) as well as other by-products, separable from 2a only by chromatography. Nopylmorpholine was oxidized to a mixture including a considerable proportion of ketone (infrared evidence) with *t*-butyl hydroperoxide. Potassium perchlorate¹⁰ failed to oxidize nopol tosylate (1c), according to tlc analysis.

Alkaline potassium permanganate¹¹ (no osmium) was also tested with 1a and yielded 40% 2a together with 3a and other by-products.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of nopol derivatives.

Nopol MEM ether diol (phenylthio)methaneboronate: Equivalent amounts of (phenylthio)methaneboronic acid and nopol MEM ether diol (2a) were refluxed 15 hr in benzene and the water separated with a Dean-Stark trap. The solution was concentrated, chromatographed with ether/petroleum ether 3:7 on silica, and distilled in a kugelrohr, oil, 78%; 100 MHz nmr (CCl₄): δ 0.88 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.29 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.8-2.3 (m, 8, CH, CH₂), 2.33 (s, 2, SCH₂B), 3.39 (s, 3, OCH₃), 3.5 (m, 6, OCH₂), 4.5 (m, partially obscured, 1, O-CH), 4.55 (s, 2, OCH₂O), 7.20 (m, 5, C₆H₅). Anal. Found: C, 63.07; H, 8.09; B, 2.62; S, 7.86. Calcd. for C₂₂H₃₃BO₅S: C, 62.86; H, 7.91; B, 2.57; S, 7.63%.

Nopol methyl ether diol butaneboronate: Nopol methyl ether diol (2b) and butaneboronic acid refluxed in benzene 90 min and the water separated with a Dean-Stark trap quantitatively yielded the boronic ester, b.p. 90° (0.03 torr); 60 MHz nmr (CCl₄): δ 1-2 (m, 23, aliphatic CH), 3.3 (s, 3, OCH₃), 3.45 (m, 2, OCH₂), 4.45 (m, 1, CHOB). Anal. Found: C, 67.95; H, 10.13; B, 3.87. Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₅BO₃: C, 68.58; H, 10.43; B, 3.86%.

Results

The nopol system (1) (Fig. 1) soon proved to be an especially sensitive and recalcitrant choice. Nopol

We next tried the VanRheenen procedure², but with the fortunate choice of trimethylamine *N*-oxide, which happened to be immediately available, in place of the recommended² *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide. Although there was no reaction of 1a in 7 days at 25° in aqueous acetone, refluxing 30 hr converted 27% to diol 2a, significantly with no detectable α-hydroxy ketone 3a or other by-products on tlc.

Pyridine is known to promote the stoichiometric reaction of osmium tetraoxide with olefins on the basis of preparative^{1,12} as well as kinetic¹³ studies, and basic conditions favour hydrolysis of osmate esters³. We therefore tried adding pyridine to our reaction mixture and on refluxing 1a in aqueous *t*-butyl alcohol 17 hr obtained 62% of diol 2a, with no by-products detectable by tlc. The yield fell to 55% after 40 hr reflux. These are among the lowest yields of the series of compounds we tested, summarized in Table 1 and may merely reflect the lability of the MEM ether group.

The diol 2a from nopol MEM ether was used to esterify (phenylthio)methaneboronic acid in the hope that the resulting boronic ester could be deprotonated at the SCH₂B group in the same manner as

TABLE I—OLEFINS WHICH HAVE BEEN *syn*-DIHYDROXYLATED BY $\text{OsO}_4/\text{Me}_3\text{NO}$ PYRIDINE.

Olefin	Yield of Diol, %
Nopol MEM ether (1a)	62
Nopol methyl ether (1b)	78
(+)- α -Pine 1e (4); (-)- α -Pine 1c	90-96
<i>cis</i> and <i>trans</i> Ethyl chrysanthemumate (6)	91
<i>E</i> - $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CHCH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	78
Cyclooctene	85
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	83
<i>E</i> - $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COCH}_3$	48

pinacol (phenylthio)methaneboronate¹⁴, with the possibility of using the resulting anion for directed chiral syntheses. However, it appears that this methylene group is too hindered for this purpose, and several attempts gave low yields of alkylation product under the usual conditions¹⁴, while quenching with deuterium oxide gave only partial deuteration, based on nmr spectra. As a result of these failures, the boronic ester serves merely as an exotic derivative to prove the presence of the *cis*-diol group in 2a.

Nopol methyl ether (1b) yielded diol 2b. The butaneboronic ester derivative proved inert toward dichloromethyl lithium and thus could not be used for chiral synthesis by homologation⁶. These failures of boronic ester chemistry led us to abandon the series of nopol derivatives at this point in favour of a less hindered system.

The conversion of (+)- α -pinene (4) to (+)-pinanediol (5) (Fig. 2), the diol which proved useful in chiral synthesis⁶, has been carried out routinely with high yields. One gram of osmium tetroxide is sufficient to convert two moles of α -pinene. It appears that the trimethylamine evolved during the reaction may play an essential role, since inadvertent vigorous refluxing of the reaction mixture reduced the yield and produced by-products¹⁵.

Fig. 2. Hydroxylation of (+)- α -pinene.

Unexpectedly, *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide⁹ proved considerably less effective than trimethylamine *N*-oxide in the oxidation of α -pinene (4) to pinanediol (5). There was no reaction after 24 hr at 25°, the "usual" conditions⁹, and the yield of diol 5 after 24 hr reflux was only 63%. Pyridine not only failed to help, but lowered the yield of 5 to 36-44% and caused formation of a substantial amount of undistillable residue. We also tested

pyridine *N*-oxide with 4 but found no 5 by tlc after 24 hr reflux.

The trimethylamine *N*-oxide/pyridine/osmium tetroxide system was tested for generality with several other olefins (Table I). The conversion of ethyl chrysanthemumate (6) (*cis/trans* mixture) to the corresponding diol (7) illustrates compatibility with ester and cyclopropane functions (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Hydroxylation of ethyl chrysanthemumate.

Disubstituted olefins react smoothly, and the yield of cyclooctanediol was slightly better than that from the *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide method. A tetrasubstituted olefin, tetramethylethylene, was converted to pinacol in better yield than the previously reported 72% with *t*-butyl hydroperoxide as oxidizing agent⁹. *N*-Methylmorpholine *N*-oxide has been reported to fail with a tetrasubstituted olefin⁴. It should be noted that most of our yields are from single attempts and are not necessarily optimum.

The usual oxidation conditions proved marginally successful with an α,β -unsaturated ketone, *E*-3-methyl-3-penten-2-one, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COCH}_3$, which yielded 48% of a single diol, $\text{CH}_3\text{CHOHCOH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COCH}_3$, after separation from tarry by-products. No detectable diol (by nmr) was formed after 39 days at 20-25° and the recovered 3-methyl-3-penten-2-one was contaminated with a gross amount of unidentified unsaturated by-products.

Hausser and Rhee have successfully applied our method to a disubstituted olefin bearing amide and ester substituents and obtained 92% of lactonized product¹⁶.

In summary, the osmium tetroxide catalyzed oxidation of olefins by trimethylamine *N*-oxide in the presence of pyridine provides a convenient and efficient general method for preparing 1,2-diols.

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